

Data-based condition assessment of a T-beam bridge with orthotropic plate using strain measurements

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ABSTRACT

A large number of steel bridges in Germany is in a critical condition. Increasing traffic volumes and higher axle loads, bridges were not designed for, lead to a high damage potential. The use of Structural Health Monitoring allows the continuous sensor-based observation of critical areas in order to record the long-term progression of the structural condition and to detect damages at an early stage. This paper presents the implementation of the monitoring fatigue sensitive details by strain measurements applied to a steel bridge with orthotropic deck plates.

Cracks in orthotropic deck plates often occur at the welded joints between longitudinal deck plate stiffeners and cross girders. Fatigue relevant stresses in welded joints and heat affected zones are determined using extrapolated strain measurements based on the structural hot spot stress concept. This procedure allows for a realistic determination of the traffic loads impact on the bridge and an accurate damage prediction.

For a comprehensive analysis of the structure condition and the load transfer within the orthotropic deck plate, as well as to investigate its vulnerability to fatigue, a digital twin of the bridge was created by means of a finite element model. This approach allows a holistic view of both, the impact and resistance sides of the structure. In order to generate reliable condition and prognosis statements, damage parameters, so-called key performance indicators (KPI), are developed. The calculated damage is finally compared with detected cracks in the welded joints of this orthotropic deck plate in order to classify the current bridge condition.

Keywords: Orthotropic Plate, Structural Health Monitoring, Asset Management

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Description of the structure

The orthotropic deck plate has been a common design since the 1930s and is still considered the standard for steel bridges. (1) Such structures have mainly a consistent design and can vary only in small details. It is therefore appropriate to investigate and develop a measurement concept on bridges with an orthotropic deck plate, as the results can be transferred to other bridges.

The structure presented in this paper is a two-span motorway bridge from 1972 with an orthotropic deck plate construction and a total length of 64.17 m. The main supporting structure consists of two parallel longitudinal girders supporting cross beams with a regular spacing of 2.02 m. *Fig. 1 a)* shows the bottom view of the bridge. The deck plate is supported by trapezoidal longitudinal stiffeners, which are welded directly between the cross girder. In addition, compared to other orthotropic deck plates, the structure has no cross beam openings in the areas of the longitudinal stiffeners. The welds at the longitudinal stiffener joints and at the connection to the deck plate are fillet welds. The thickness of the weld cannot be determined from the inventory records and is assumed to be 10 mm based on visual assessment. Moreover, the penetration depth of the weld joints cannot be specified. In addition,

the weld seam quality cannot be compared with current requirements due to the period of manufacture.

Several weld cracks have already been detected as a result of prescribed structural inspections. As the aim of this work is to investigate the remaining lifetime with regard to fatigue resistance, the focus below is on the vulnerable welded joints.

Fig. 1. a) bottom view of the bridge; b) typical existing damages

Inspection reports are available for this structure in which the damages of the last 20 years are documented. The cracks shown in Fig. 1 b) are located in the corner of the longitudinal stiffener in the joint to the cross girder. This damage is typical for longitudinal stiffeners that are welded directly between cross girders. The area is subjected to shear as well as tensile stresses. In addition, an orthotropic deck plate exhibits many such welded joint details.

1.2 Measurement concept

In (2), a comprehensive measurement concept was developed on the bridge in order to record the load situation and to analyse specifically fatigue critical weld joints in terms of the lifetime.

A total of 57 strain gauges and 9 temperature sensors are installed on this structure. Three cross girders are monitored to confirm redundancy and to be able to compensate failure of individual sensors if necessary. The sensors are positioned below the left wheel of the truck lane, as this is where the highest loads and therefore relevant fatigue stresses are to be expected. The positions of the sensors in the transverse direction (see Fig. 2 b)) are based on the half-sided design of the RQ 29.5 (3). Fig. 2 a) shows the top view of the bridge as a satellite image with the area of the sensors, as well as a transverse view of the monitored longitudinal stiffeners.

Fig. 2. a) satellite view of measurement system location (4); b) sensors positions on cross girders

To ensure that the wheel is also detected in case of lateral track drift, the sensors are distributed on three longitudinal stiffeners for each cross girder. The width of the monitored area is 1.53 m. The

middle cross girder, labelled below as measuring cross section 1 (MCS-1), is configured with the highest number of sensors.

Above each longitudinal stiffener, sensors marked in blue are mounted on the deck plate to determine the exact transverse position of the wheel.

The main function of the strain gauges marked in yellow is to record the strains in the lengthwise direction at the welded joint and to evaluate the multiaxiality of the stresses in the area of the of the longitudinal stiffener corners. It can be assumed that these straight sectors of the welded joints are less vulnerable to fatigue, therefore they are not considered in the following analyses.

The strain gauges marked in green are used to accurately measure strains in the fatigue sensitive area. In order to obtain a more precise prediction of the existing critical stresses in the weld joints, the structural hot spot stress concept (5) is used for the fatigue calculation by extrapolating the measured strains linearly and calculating them in a 1D stress state with a young's modulus of 210000 N/mm². Due to the fact that strain gauges cannot be applied directly on the weld surface, the critical stress is not to be determined directly in the hot spot. The sensors are attached as close as possible to the weld seam. The distances to the weld toe are 15.47 mm and 29.47 mm, which are slightly higher than the recommendations according to (3), which are 0.4*t and 1.0*t and would in this case correspond to 4 mm and 10 mm.

2 FE-SIMULATION

In the following part, the load situation with regard to a truck transit is analysed at the relevant joints. For this purpose, the entire bridge is modelled as a shell model and refined in the measurement area with a submodel using volume elements. It is therefore possible to achieve a minimum mesh size of 2 mm. The load acts locally on the substructure. Therefore, to determine the stresses, the load corresponding to a wheel of the fatigue load model no. 3 (6) is applied with a force of 60 kN to a square surface with an edge length of 400 mm.

2.1 Load situation and relevant load position

The knowledge of the critical load position is decisive for determining the critical load situation. Fig. 3 b) shows the load position related to and the stress for three selected strain gauges of a rolling wheel.

For this load situation, the stresses of the strain gauges directly below the wheel SG01, SG02 and SG03 are shown in Fig. 3 a). The position in the z-direction "z_pos" refers to the distance to the cross girder in the longitudinal direction of the bridge. It can therefore be determined graphically that the maximum stresses in the weld seams are occurring when the wheel is 800 mm in front of the cross girder.

Fig. 3. a) influence lines of a rolling wheel; b) load position on the cross girder

The strain gauge on the deck plate is also subjected to higher stresses if the load is in front of the cross girder. The highest stresses on the strain gauge on the deck plate are reached at a distance of 200 mm. The horizontal distance in the direction of movement between the positions at which the maximum stresses occur on the deck plate and the cross girder is therefore 600 mm. This leads to different times of the maxima in the recorded measurement results.

In general, the reason for the increased stress with higher distance of the load from the cross girder can be explained by the following approach. If the load is above the cross girder, the load is transferred by the cross girder and not by the longitudinal stiffeners in the case of an orthotropic deck plate with welded-on longitudinal stiffeners. Therefore, the load transfer through the cross girder reduces the forces in the longitudinal stiffener and thus also the resulting stresses at the positions of the strain gauges.

2.2 Comparison of structural and notch stresses of welded joints

The measurement concept is used to determine the fatigue damage based on calculation of the stresses at the welded joints using the structural hot spot stress concept. Fig. 4 a) shows graphically the stress distribution in the corner area of longitudinal stiffeners. The related load is located 800 mm in front of the cross girder in the longitudinal direction of the bridge, so that the maximum stress is generated as shown in chapter 2.1.

In the figure, the colour highlighted stresses are transformed in the measuring direction of the one-dimensional strain gauges. The black dots represent the positions of strain gauges no. 3 and 4 (SG3, SG4), which are used as support points for extrapolating the stress at the weld toe. Due to the fact that the longitudinal stiffener is only connected to the cross member by the weld joint, compressive stresses (blue area) occur in the cross member below the weld seam, especially in the corner area. Tensile stresses (red area) occur above the weld seam in the corner area. The compressive stresses are about five times higher than the tensile stresses. The maximum tension stress of the cross girder at the point $\sigma_{t,max,CB}$ is 13.35 N/mm², whereas the maximum compressive stress $\sigma_{c,max,CB}$ in the weld joint is -65.99 N/mm². The analysed point, for which the hotspot stress is calculated according to the structural hot spot stress concept, is about 3 mm in front of the position of the maximum compressive stress.

Fig. 4. a) illustration of the structural hot spot stress concept and the axial stresses of the strain gauge;
b) comparison of notch stress and structural hot spot stress concept of the FE results

Fig. 4 b) shows the qualitative comparison of the structural and notch stress at the hotspot. The notch stress is extracted in the FE model over a path of 10 steps between the hot spot and strain gauge no. 3. The stresses show the non-linear notch stress curve and decrease with increasing distance from the hot spot. The maximum stress σ_{notch} is around 63 N/mm². It should be noted that the value is only an approximation, as there is a singularity at the hot spot in the FE model. For an exact calculation of the notch stress using FEA, further parameters such as finer meshing and the design of a concave fillet weld must be considered (5).

Therefore, the structural hot spot stress is compared with the notch stress. The hot spot stress is extracted at the positions of the strain gauges and extrapolated linearly. The stress of -27.93 N/mm² at SG 3 and -38.89 N/mm² at SG 4 lead to a hot spot stress σ_{HS} of -51.01 N/mm², which is about 19% less than the expected notch stress at the hot spot.

The FE simulation shows that the stresses at the fatigue sensitive welded joint decrease with increasing distance from the hot spot. Therefore, the stresses at the hot spot can be calculated approximately using the structural hot spot stress concept and the welded joint fatigue can be determined more precisely.

3 MONITORING DATA ANALYSIS

3.1 Detection of Events

The aim of event recording is to reduce the amount of data on site in real time and analyse only those events that are relevant for fatigue calculation. The strain gauges on the deck plate are used for the event detection, as they are directly elongated by loads on the bridge surface. As the position of the wheel and therefore the strain gauge with the highest load is unknown when the vehicle passes, the largest value of all deck plate strain gauges of a cross girder is considered at all times. The envelope curve function of the deck plate strain gauges for MCS-1 is shown in *Fig. 5 a)* for a monitoring period of 30 s (3000 data points) and in *Fig. 5 b)* for one event with a period of 1 sec (100 data points). As a result, the reliability of the event detection is also increased because the triggering is not only dependent on a single strain gauge.

Fig. 5. a) 6 detected events with start and end within 30 seconds of monitoring; b) semitrailer combination and measurement data for one event (background image: (7))

In order to detect only heavy vehicles, a threshold must be defined so that measurements are analysed when this value is reached. To determine this limit value, the number of detected vehicle events is iteratively compared with those of a BAST continuous measurement counting station (8). The limit value is conservatively set at 2 N/mm^2 for the entire measurement period (green line in *Fig. 5 a)*).

A second parameter for event detection and delimiting in time is the distance between two consecutive events. This can be illustrated by the following assumption. The EU Council Directive 96/53/EG (9) specify the maximum length of an articulated truck as 16.5 m. Current developments show that platooning allows several trucks to be controlled together, reducing the safety distance to around 15 m (10). This results in a minimum distance of 31.5 m. The maximum permissible speed for trucks on motorways in Germany is 80 km/h (§3 StVO (11)). Under the conservative assumption that this speed is exceeded by approximately 10 km/h, the duration can be determined as 1.26 s. At a measurement frequency of 100 Hz, the minimum number of measurement points between two events is 126 indices. In order to delimit a vehicle event in time, the time at which the first wheel passes over the first cross girder and the last wheel passes over the third cross girder is determined.

3.2 Combination of cross girder and deck plate strain gauges values

The vehicle transit in this example (see *Fig. 5 b)*) involves a semitrailer combination with a two axles truck and three axles directly behind each other of the semitrailer. In (6), the wheel spacings are usually specified as 3.2 m, 5.2 m, 1.3 m and 1.3 m. This type of vehicle is common in Germany, with a 50% proportion of heavy goods traffic for long-distance routes (6). In the following section the stresses on the MCS-1 will be analysed, as this is where most of the sensors are mounted and the analysis can be carried out most comprehensively. The upper graph in *Fig. 6* shows the measured values of the strain gauges on the deck plate. The lower graph shows the calculated stress values of the strain gauges on the cross girder, which are closer to the weld joint. When comparing the curves, it is noticeable that the sensors on the cross girder permanently record vibrations. The curves result qualitatively from the superposition of a stimulated sinusoidal oscillation and the deflection caused by the load. The vibration amplitude increases with approaching wheel to the measurement cross-section.

Fig. 6. comparison of the measured values of the strain gauges of the cross girder and the deck plate for a single transit event

Before the event, no vibrations are recognisable from the measured values of the strain gauges on the deck plate. After the event, slight vibrations are present, but fade quickly. It can be assumed that the vibrations are not detected by an event, but rather the natural resonance of the deck plate due to the impulse excitation of the vehicle. In addition, it cannot be excluded that vibrations from other vehicles on the bridge are also detected, so that the absolute stress values are influenced by constructive or destructive interference. However, as the measurement system calculates the actual fatigue of the welded joints, the interference can be neglected.

As it cannot be excluded that the extrapolated stresses of the structural hot spot stress concept from vibrations also have a fatigue effect on the weld joints, a period of 2 s before and after the vehicle event is also analysed.

The evaluation is carried out by counting and classifying stress hysteresis using the rainflow algorithm (12). The accumulation of damage is carried out by summing the quotient of the actual number and limit load cycle number from the S/N curve for each class.

4 FATIGUE CALCULATION AND DETERMINATION OF KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

In this chapter, the fatigue calculation procedure and the comparison of the calculated damage with real conditions are described. The results of different detail categories for different fatigue sensitive locations are also discussed.

4.1 Determination of structural fatigue class

Table B.1 in DIN EN 1993-1-9 (13) is used to determine a suitable fatigue class, but no structural detail is provided for the structural hot spot stresses that represents the existing geometry and load situation sufficiently. With regard to the geometry and crack initiation, case 5 can be used as an approximation. The reference value of the fatigue curve $\Delta\sigma_c$ for this detail category is 100 N/mm². To check the suitability of fatigue class 100, the damage must be calculated over a time period and the expected durability of the welded detail must be determined and compared with the crack initiation age.

Table 1 shows the durability for selected welded joints. The selection is based on the weld joints with the highest stress on each cross girder HS18_17, HS40_39, HS53_52. The hot spot labelling depends on the numbering of the strain gauges, which are located in the corner of the longitudinal stiffener. The calculated durability is based on a data set of eleven months and is listed in the table assuming reference values $\Delta\sigma_c$ of 50 N/mm², 56 N/mm² and 100 N/mm².

Table 1. service life for selected welded joints for different fatigue detail assumptions

MCS	hot spot	fatigue class		
		50 [a]	56 [a]	100 [a]
MCS-1	HS18_17	38.4	66.6	3742.9
MCS-2	HS40_39	17.6	28.9	866.5
MCS-3	HS53_52	10.5	16.6	357.5
	average:	22.2	37.4	1655.6

The welded joints on the measurement cross-sections show different levels of damage. The damage is predicted to be about half as big for MCS-1 as for MCS-2 and MCS-3. Therefore the last row of the table shows the mean value of the durability for all measurement cross-sections.

Using fatigue class 100, the durability of the weld joints would be classified as far too high. Even the most highly loaded welded joint achieves an expected service life of 357.5 a, which is well above the bridge age with several fatigue cracks. If the fatigue class 100 is used to assess the condition, theoretically no cracks would occur in the weld joints. Therefore, a structure-specific detail category is selected that links the time of occurrence of a crack with the predicted service lifetime. The difficulty exists in determining the time of the first crack.

The first available inspection report (2002) of the bridge at an age of 30 years confirmed first cracks. It is assumed that the period after the occurrence of the first crack is 30 years, even if the crack may have occurred earlier. To select a suitable reference value, the expected durability must therefore be determined iteratively between the detail categories 50 N/mm² and 56 N/mm². In order to determine the fatigue of the welded details and assess their condition, the reference value of fatigue resistance $\Delta\sigma_c$ of 53 N/mm² is used in the following evaluations.

4.2 Service lifetime calculation and condition assessment

For the durability calculation, it is assumed that the number of vehicles and the axle loads are constant in the past and future. As in section 4.1, the data is based on measurements over a period of eleven months. The service lifetime is calculated as the reciprocal of the damage extrapolated to one year. Table 2 shows the service lifetime of the welded joints based on the fatigue calculation using the reference value for the fatigue strength $\Delta\sigma_c$ of 53 N/mm².

Table 2. service lifetime for monitored welded joints

MCS	hot spot	total lifetime [a]
MCS-1	3_4	3549
	8_7	419
	13_14	348
	18_17	51
	23_24	290
MCS-2	34_33	456897
	36_37	85
	40_39	23
	43_42	462
MCS-3	47_46	33
	50_49	100
	53_52	13
	56_55	492

The remaining service life results from the calculated service life less the age of the building of 50 years at the time of evaluation. The welded joints have different total lifetimes depending on their position, ranging from 13 years for HS53_52 to 492 years for HS56_55.

Three hotspots have a total service lifetime that is less than the current age of the bridge. According to the quantitative values, cracks should already be present at the weld joints HS53_52, HS40_39, HS47_46, but these are not yet visible. In particular, the welded joints below the middle stiffener are significantly vulnerable, but currently show no indications of damage. Other details that could exhibit cracks in the future are HS18_17, HS36_37 and HS50_49, as these also have a low remaining service lifetime of less than 50 years in relation to the age of the structure compared to the other weld joints. HS8_7, HS13_14, HS23_24, HS43_42 and HS56_55 have a long remaining service lifetime, so it can be assumed that no damage will occur to these weld joints in the future.

It is noticeable that the three highly stressed welded joints HS40_39, HS18_17 and HS53_52 are located one behind the other on the same longitudinal stiffener in the direction of traffic. It can therefore be assumed that these details are significantly stressed by the truck lane.

Fig. 7 shows the welded joints of HS3_4 and HS34_33. For both joints, there is a visible crack in the weld toe to the cross girder. This is significantly noticeable in the results, as the calculated service lifetimes are very high compared to the other weld joints, which have no visible cracks. It can be assumed that the stresses from the longitudinal stiffeners are not transferred to the cross girder and therefore the relevant fatigue stresses are low and the calculated service lifetime is therefore very high. For this reason, the two welded joints are marked in grey in *Table 2*.

In addition the detail HS47_46 is located at the same point in the direction of travel as the before described details. Thus, as already mentioned above, this welded joint can be assigned a high risk.

Fig. 7. existing cracks in monitored weld joints

It should be noted that the quantitative values for the calculation of the remaining service lifetime are theoretical values based on the following assumptions. Firstly, it is assumed that the first welded joint occurs after 30 years and the reference value for the fatigue strength of 53 N/mm² is based on this assumption.

In addition, there are already visible and invisible fatigue cracks at the weld joints, which individually influences the fatigue results due to stress redistribution at the details. Furthermore, the welded joints are subject to different execution qualities, which affect the calculation.

A condition statement based on quantitative lifetimes is therefore absolutely not possible, but a probability of failure can be made by comparing the damage to the welded joints.

As the measurement concept only detects a small part of the bridge, a statistical occurrence of damage at the bridge can be determined from the data. 13 details are monitored, of which approx. 40 % show a low susceptibility to fatigue. 20 % are in a critical condition. Another 20 % require more stringent checks during structural maintenance and 15 % already exhibited cracks before the measuring system was installed.

4.3 Accumulated damage over the measurement period

The following section considers the theoretical increase in damage over the time of measurement. *Fig. 8* shows the damage accumulated over a period of 16 months and additionally the weekly average component temperature of the central cross girder (MCS-1). The damage progression is analysed using the most stressed welded joint HS18_17 of MCS-1 (red line).

Fig. 8. accumulated fatigue in comparison with the component temperature of the cross girder

When considering the period from July to September 2022 and 2023, the weekly rhythm of truck traffic can be identified. Due to the lower volume of heavy goods vehicles at weekends, the graph shows a gradual progression. This pattern is also recognisable in a weaker form in the winter months. In addition, a significant dependence of the damage gradients on the temperature can be recognised. The fatigue damage of the welded joint is higher in summer than in winter. For example, for the welded detail mentioned above, damage of 0.0004 per month is recorded in winter/spring, while in summer/autumn the damage gradients are around five to six times as high at 0.0022 per month. The cross beam temperature is between 15°C in December 2022 and 38°C in August 2022 and July 2023. According to (14) the modulus of elasticity of asphalt is temperature-dependent, among other parameters, and is lower at higher temperatures. For this reason, the measured stresses in the welded joints are higher, as the load is transferred more centrally into the surface layer. At lower temperatures in winter, the loads are distributed over a larger area due to the higher stiffness of the asphalt, which reduces the stresses in the welded details.

The seasonal and weekly progression of damage can be recognised in the same way for all monitored welding details at almost constant traffic. It is therefore important to consider a measurement period > 1 year, as otherwise the seasonal influence of the component and asphalt temperature cannot be assessed.

5 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

As part of this work, an FE simulation of the bridge was first carried out. By analysing a rolling wheel, it was possible to determine that positioning the wheel 0.8 m in front of the cross girder leads to maximum stresses in the critical areas.

In addition, measurement data from strain sensors was recorded to determine the stresses at the weld seams. To reduce the data, events are filtered and the fatigue of the details is calculated for each vehicle. The stresses are extrapolated to the weld toes using the structural hot spot stress concept. As standards do not provide a realistic detail category, a structure specific reference value for fatigue resistance was determined. Due to the different calculated damage to the welded joints resulting from both high loads and different execution qualities of the welds, a key performance indicator is expressed by the probability of failure in a comparison of the fatigue.

The analysis shows an increased risk of fatigue in weld joints where damage has already occurred in the same place on other cross beams and which are located directly under the truck lane.

Weld seams with existing damage have a very long calculated service lifetimes due to stress redistributions. Future investigations can therefore analyse damage over a longer period of time and evaluate damage gradients in order to detect stress redistributions and resulting cracks.

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